

DESIRED FUTURES FOR ARCTIC INDUSTRIES FINDING A BALANCE BETWEEN TRADITIONS AND NEW GROWTH

ArcticHubs (2020-2024) is a Horizon EU project that develops tools to promote sustainable development of industrial and cultural hubs in the Arctic.

This policy brief focuses on recommendations for Arctic stakeholders and industrial actors outside the Arctic based on the future work of the ArcticHubs project.

The value of futures studies lies in opening minds to consider new possibilities and changes in the operating environment and to be prepared and act faster or earlier. In the ArcticHubs project, futures studies have been used together with local and indigenous actors to find out what are the common nominators of desirable futures for Arctic regions and industries.

The ability to anticipate provides time to better understand threats and opportunities and to develop more creative strategies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

FOR ALL ACTIVITIES IN THE ARCTIC REGION

- Promote transparency and inclusiveness in decision-making
- Create models for attracting and keeping residents

FOR ARCTIC LIVELIHOODS

TOURISM

- Prioritise quality over quantity
- Study and test tourism fees or taxes

MINING

- Invest time for informal communication in addition to formal meetings

FORESTRY

- Involve all relevant stakeholders in a forest forum

AQUACULTURE

- Take environmental impacts into attention more carefully

REINDEER HERDING & OTHER INDIGENOUS LIVELIHOODS

- Pay special attention to cumulative land use impacts

WHAT DO WE MEAN BY ARCTIC HUBS?

Hubs are nodes hosting either a combination of economic activities, or one main industry or means of livelihood, where the challenges and impacts facing the Arctic region are tangible and acute.

The Arctic hubs in the project fall into categories of fish farming, forestry, tourism, mining and indigenous cultural hubs. The learning hubs outside the Arctic provide points for comparison with the Arctic cases.

More information: <https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs/hubs/>.

HIGHLIGHTS OF ARCTICHUBS' FUTURE WORK

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|-----------------|--------------------------|---------------------------|
| 1. Kemi | 7. Gran Sameby | 12. Egersund |
| 2. Kemijärvi | 8. Gällivare | 13. Westfjords |
| 3. Inari | 9. Kautokeino-Kvalsund | 14. Nuup Kangerlua |
| 4. Kittilä | 10. Varangerfjord | 15. Suðuroy |
| 5. Jokkmokk | 11. Svalbard | |
| 6. Malå | | |

"Indigenous knowledge should be recognised"

Nuuk/Nuup Kangerlua, GL

"How can we in Malå make Brussels understand our reality?"

Malå, SE

"Rebuilding trust with Russia will take a long time"

Varanger, NO

"It is easier to influence tourism than heavily concentrated fish farming"

Suðuroy, FO

"Tourists should know that huskies are not part of the original Sámi culture"

Inari, FI

"Investing in road network would improve the quality of life for residents"

Westfjords, IS

"Policies increasingly restrict forest use"

Finnish-Swedish forestry hub

RECOMMENDATIONS IN DETAIL

ARCTIC IN GENERAL

Promote transparency and inclusiveness in decision-making

The involvement of local people in decision-making and planning is the most important issue that comes up in all work on the future. It is important for both public authorities and business representatives to think creatively and contextually about potential stakeholders and their interests.

Create models for attracting and keeping residents

Demographic challenges are present all-over Arctic areas. Clarifying the immigration and work permit processes would help to attract new residents. Creating more opportunities for remote work to attract and retain residents in Arctic communities is needed.

TOURISM

Prioritise quality over quantity

Overtourism is a seasonal problem in the most popular places in the Arctic. Regulation, zoning and strategic planning would be answers to the problem. Public dialogue is needed. In Greenland, for example, a new Tourism Act has been drafted.

Study and test tourism fees or taxes

In most destinations it is hoped that the local level will benefit more from tourism. In many places there is a desire to explore and experiment with tourism taxes or charges, although there are also doubts.

MINING

Invest time for informal communication in addition to formal meetings

Mining is viewed with scepticism and will require different approaches from both the mining industry and national regulators to make it locally acceptable. Trust must be earned, especially on environmental issues. In the case of Nussir in Norway, a communication strategy targeting relevant stakeholders and efforts to increase visibility and awareness are proving fruitful.

FORESTRY

Involve all relevant stakeholders to forest dialogue

Issues such as the protection of old-growth forests and communication between forestry and reindeer husbandry are proving difficult.

The need for holistic planning and cooperation is obvious. In Inari, for example, there is a desire for a comprehensive forest management plan. There is a need for softer 'Lean forestry' methods in forest management that respect more the needs of other land use modes.

RECOMMENDATIONS IN DETAIL

AQUACULTURE

Take environmental impacts into attention more carefully

Stricter regulation is needed for sustainable production methods. Aquaculture practices should be strengthened to reduce environmental impacts and ensure the health of fjord ecosystems. Diversifying the sector by exploring alternative aquaculture methods, such as offshore and multi-trophic systems, would reduce the environmental footprint and increase sustainability.

REINDEER HERDING & OTHER INDIGENOUS LIVELIHOODS

Pay special attention to cumulative land use impacts

Ever-increasing land uses put pressure on reindeer herding, especially when different activities are not coordinated and their interactions are not considered. Grazing areas are reduced and grazing rotation becomes more difficult. More research is needed on the effects of energy production and other land use changes, especially wind power, on reindeer husbandry and other traditional livelihoods.

CONCLUSIONS

Local empowerment and balancing industrial growth with environmental sustainability are key issues across the Arctic region. **Effective participation and early involvement of local communities** in planning processes is essential for sustainable development and attracting new residents. Particular attention needs to be paid to **indigenous peoples' participation** and dialogue. It is also important to **maximise local benefits** from extractive industries.

National governments are key players in regulation. **Municipalities** also have a very important role to play, as they are expected to facilitate discussions and negotiations between different parties and stakeholders, and in general to bring different actors together. Municipalities also play an important role in **land use planning**, which is crucial in times of climate change and green transition.

For all actors in the Arctic, **dialogue with local people** is of paramount importance. Different voices need to be heard and taken into account in order to create a sustainable future.

HOW THE WORK WAS DONE?

The future work of the Arctic Hubs started with a Delphi survey in several regions, with respondents also from the national level. These results formed the basis for future workshops that brought together a wide range of stakeholders in each hub region.

In these workshops, scenarios up to 2035 were developed in order to share local insights with decision-makers and industry players operating in Arctic regions. The scenarios were then evaluated by both local and external experts. The work was concluded by organising broader future forums in some of the hub regions and at joint Arctic events.

ARCTICHUBS IN BRIEF

The EU-funded ArcticHubs project (2020–2024) develops solution-oriented tools, guidelines, and future scenarios for Arctic communities, industrial stakeholders, policymakers and other relevant actors.

The Arctic Hubs project assists in the creation and implementation of regional development strategies aimed at reconciling new economic opportunities with traditional livelihoods and solving land use conflicts between different actors.

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MORE INFORMATION

<https://projects.luke.fi/arctichubs>

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